

**TEACHING CHILDREN WITH SPECIAL NEEDS IN INCLUSIVE SETTING IN NIGERIA:
PROFESSIONAL ISSUES**

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Abstract

The paper discussed children with special needs as any child whose performance of any sort deviate from that of the regular children either below or above average to such a degree that special needs education Programmes are designed and carried out for their success in life. Inclusive education is the latest Trend in general education in the provision of placement alternative programme that seeks more effective and meaningful education for all children. The paper discussed teachers' preparation as simply to mean arrangement, plan, and strategies for effective, prudent and upstanding for quality, teaching activities that needs dedication commitment, and sacrifice to be willingly taken to work with these children. The professionalism here calls for specialized service delivery that can only be provided by proficient teachers with sound professional orientation. The teacher needs the professional competence in inter-personal relationships, Communication, ethics and integrity. The paper dwelled at the personality of the professional teacher as the sum total of the person. The challenges the professional teacher faces in terms of full acceptance and accommodation of the child with special needs, the expected functions teachers should perform in the inclusive education setting are copious. The paper concludes with suggestions that all special needs education teachers should go for further training in development studies as special needs education is changing with the trend of events in the world today.

Keywords: Special Needs Education; Teacher Preparation; Inclusive Education; Professionalism; Children with Special Needs

Introduction

We live in a world as Mangal (2009) reiterated full of diversities. Every form of living and non-living things are very special, unique and different from each other in one way or the other. It is very wonderful that we lack words to appreciate the creativity of God. When we see that no single thing He created has exact behavior of the other. For example, the identical twins. As a result a child is born into this world with its own unique abilities and capacities of body and mind. Thus, some are fortunate enough to have extraordinary abilities, intelligence, capabilities or abilities while others are at average level or even suffer from many problems since birth. The gap between the abilities and inabilities of the children related to their learning, development and adjustment of life found at the time of their birth may further be widened by the nature of their environmental differences and parental up bringing them pass-through in feeding and education. This results in labeling them as children who are exceptionally superior or “disabled”, capable or incapable in one or other areas of their personality and educational development. They are the children with special education needs.

There have been many attempts by people and authorities to define who a child with special needs, is based on their behaviors and performance. Whether the child is a boy or girl and the place of origin is in Nigeria or not, Ikwulono (2012) agreed that he/she can be more easily described than defined. There are those who maintain that the term children with special needs refers to any child whose performance deviates from the normal below or above

average to such a degree that regular special education programming (modification or enrichment) is designed and carried out for their success in life. Some believe that, the child with special needs is a child who is intellectually talented and gifted or a child who excels in one skill or another e.g. (wood carvings, smitten, singing, acting, reading etc.) which could either be in the physical or intellectual skills. Others see children with hearing or the visually impaired, the behavior disordered or the socially maladjusted belonging to this group. However, professionals in other fields and authorities in special education needs came to accept the term as referring to children who are considered a normal trend of development by the larger segment of the population. On a more general note, Children which special needs refers to both talented and the gifted and other categories of children with disabilities. Heward and Orlansky (1984) Kirk and Gallagher (1986), and Abang (1981) stated that the advantage of using the term special needs, is that a more elaborate meaning of who special needs persons are has become clear since both categories (those with disabilities and the gifted) are put together because of their special educational needs. The manner of the deviation, Winzer (1990) and Mangal (2009) are either in:

Sensory abilities: like audition visio, taction, Neuromotor: this is in respect of physical disorder or handicap, Social behavior disorders like autism spectrum disorder, Communication abilities: speech, and language disorders., Mental characteristic: Mental disorder, Learning disabilities: and intellectual deficit , physical handicap, Ill-health and Gifted and talented.

The level of the individual exceptionalities could range from mild to profound. The deviation could be significant that the child is not able to function well within the community and or the school consequently (Ikwulono 2016). They need inclusive educational services with a professional teacher to enable them develop their potentials. It is in this light that one can say that the child's deviation in any area must be such that the normal school curriculum needs to be with professional issues modified before the child can benefit from the education.

Concept of Inclusive Education

Since time immemorial, people with special educational needs have a long history of isolation, discrimination, rejection, ambivalence and stereotype attitude because of perceived poor academic performance in school, low self-esteem and withdrawal to self-elective mutism from the mainstream of the society. Human beings by nature are found to have strong reservations for those who appear to deviate or differ in emotions, behavior and cognition, sensory and social attributes from many people in one way or the other in the society. They need total inclusion in all facets of life. Inclusive education represents the latest trend in the provisions of placement or alternative programme in the field of general education to children with special educational needs. Giangreco and Giangreco (1997) asserted that inclusive education is a set of values, principles and practices that seek more effective and meaningful education for all children regardless of whether they have exceptional labels or not. In a related move, Advani and Chadla (2003) argued that inclusive education is that type of education that provides a favorable setting to achieve equal opportunity and full participation for all. This brings children with special needs well within the purview of a school setting. Inclusive education recognizes the different needs of the child and ensures equal education for all through appropriate curriculum, teaching strategies, support services and participation by parents and the community. This is to say that all children with or without exceptionalities learn together in the same setting.

Special Education Teaching Preparation

Teacher preparation simply means arrangement, plans and strategies that are made for effective, prudent and upstanding for quality teaching activities. The success of any meaningful educational programme is dependent solely on availability and readiness of the teachers. This means that teachers are the strong holds of quality education to thrive. Bajah (1983) noted that a teacher is not a teacher without professional proficiency. In addition,

Unaegbu (2004) agreed that one is not a teacher if the proficiency of the teaching is not there and used. This is perhaps why Abang (1995) reiterated that teaching people with special needs is not a profession to venture into by just anybody as a last venture for employment. This implies that teaching in inclusive setting is a very special profession to be held in high esteem and never to be undervalued. It is a profession that needs dedication, commitment and sacrifice to the cause of people with special education needs and should be taken willingly by those who have the interest and desire to work with children with special needs at heart.

However, Special teacher preparation, Turkman and Monetti (2011) observed that it is to produce practical knowledge about inclusive education of children with special needs in education and behaviors. This is to say that

1. It helps teachers understand issues like how the students learn in the classroom
2. what motivates them to learn as they are learning
3. how to design instructional programmes that maximize learning in children
4. How to access students, learning and curriculum for adaptation and modification
5. For effectiveness. It helps teachers to become more aware of their thoughts and actions and understand the effects, these thoughts and actions have on other people in and outside inclusive education settings.

The special education teacher's job is rewarding yet with challenges. The preparation helps them to meet these challenges of inadequate materials, equipment, and conducive school environment of inclusive education and be more effective Practitioners as education foster. Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004) saw education as the worth and development of the individual and for the general development of the society. More so, every child should have a right to equal educational opportunities irrespective of any real or imagined exceptionality according to the child's ability. The need for the professionalism is to acquire the appropriate skills, the development of mental, physical and social abilities, and competencies as equipment for the professional teacher to live and contribute to the development of inclusive education in Nigeria.

Professional Issue in Teacher Preparation

In discussing the special education teacher preparation for the future, Nwazuoke (1996) called for specialized service delivery which can only be provided by proficient teachers with sound professional orientation. This implies that special education is a specialty itself based on the special teaching methods, instructional materials, specialized trained teachers and the individuals involved. It is observed that, everybody has the right to optimum development in his or her potential, and that every person has a unique set of potential, interest, goals, percepts liabilities and assets. Teachers preparation for the future entails step by step training and competencies required for general and unique curriculum In teaching children with special education needs.

Winzer (1990) Contended that the major emphasis in education of children with hearing impairment is placed on development of language and evolution of communication skills. They are the most important vehicles through which the child processes information and expresses himself or herself. The children with visual impairment do not see and do not learn by the normal way of imitation and observation. According to Rogow (1987), they learn a new and different set of alphabets and reading style from the conventional method of reading by sight. The emotional interaction between the mobility instructor and the child is an essential element in the successful outcome of mobility training. The training process does not only consist merely of transfer of information from the instructor to the child, the interplay of personal factors can affect the outcome of instruction.

The patience, interest and knowledgibility to teach children with behavior disorder in daily-living-skills and rehabilitation matters most in professionalism for the special education teacher for the task ahead as in all

relationships between individuals, Rogow (1987) stressed that positive and negative feelings, Personal characteristics, beliefs and attitudes of the teacher interfere to facilitate their interactions.

Professionalism shall continue to be highly rated in inclusive education for National development plans. As it is the most important instrument of change in all human endeavors. Federal Government of Nigeria (2004) documented that any fundamental change in the intellectual, social, political outlook of any society has to be preceded by professionalisms. Ozoji (1989) reported that most of the teachers of the visually impaired claimed that they could handle much of the skills involved in teaching the children with visual impairment. These same teachers were not so confident about handling special education (unique) curriculum and they expressed urgent need for training in the curriculum context for quality assurance.

Professional Competencies for Teacher Preparation

A special education teacher who should be referred to as specialist needs the professional training in special education to be able to provide services such as the dynamic curriculum in inclusive education. Due to the necessity and dynamism in curricular context, Ozoji (1986) and Adima (1988) stated that the teacher should have the following credentials to enable him teach children in inclusive setting, identifying their individual differences, abilities in disabilities, area of needs, interests and methods of meeting such needs like in these areas:

1. **Intellectual Ability:** These include ability to observe, gather, select and evaluate facts, ability to learn easily and quickly; synthesize and generalize facts, creative imagination, original and logical thinking.
2. **Interpersonal Relationship:** This implies the ability to understand people and work with them, tolerance and respect for other people, ability to evaluate people's reaction to gain trust and respect, courtesy and good manners.
3. **Communication:** This is the ability to persuade and motivate people, listening skills, fluency in oral and written expression, fluency in sign language, interests, zeal and determination to teach and train people.
4. **Intellectual and Emotional Maturity:** This implies stability of behavior and action, ability to act with poise and in calm and objective manners and independent in drawing unbiased conclusion to issues.
5. **Ethics and Integrity:** This include the genuine desire to help others, humility to accept facts and learn from other people, Acceptance to recognize the limitation of competence, ability to keep records "straight" and well secured and consciousness in supplying the right information when and as appropriate.

In the same vein, Ikwulono (2012) added that competencies include:

Patience: The teacher has to exercise a good degree of patience with the child, school and parents because of the unique problems of learning patterns, behavioral and social characteristics.

Acceptance: The teacher should understand and accept the child for who the child is as a fellow human being that misfortune befell from a different socio-cultural environment.

Tolerance: Teachers should learn to tolerate the slow progress of the children in learning as they are expected in their usual characteristics as slow learners and repeat tasks to encourage their abilities.

Creativity: The teacher should be creative in the choice and use of appropriate instructional materials in teaching for quality learning to take place and the development of hidden skills and talents.

Sequence: The teacher should present the lesson in good step-by-step manner. Thus, starting from the known to the unknown, simple to complex, concrete to abstract to meet the needs of each child in the learning environment.

Adaptability: The teacher should adapt and adjust to the learner's behavior because of the psychology of individual differences as they sometimes behave irrationally without realizing the consequences of their behaviors.

Counseling: The teacher should be able to establish and maintain good relationship with the learners and being able to change from one teaching method to the other to stimulate and motivate learning process as they look on to him as their role model.

Personality of the Teacher in Inclusive Education

To discuss inclusive education in education management without the personality of the teacher is complete. Good classroom management, Abang (1989) reiterated it will be possible if the teacher provides effective leadership that requires authority and possession of leadership qualities. Personality attributes of the teacher are the knowledge and mastery of the subject, good health, self-confidence, dedication, sense of humor, discipline, sincerity, patience, stable emotion, improvisation, responsibility and leadership. Thus, personality is the individual differences in characteristics patterns of thinking, feeling and behaving. It is the sum total of a teacher. The personality attributes of a teacher are very important to the learners' parents, and the society because of its sensitive function as a model, for the learners. Teachers have the authority on some aspects of the culture of the community to assist children. The teacher is someone who trains people for some occupation and acts as an agent of selection in the competition for employment and higher education studies. As the teacher has delicate and important roles to play in classroom management in an inclusive setting for children with disabilities, he is all the time under observation and evaluation by the outside world. Inclusive education recognizes the many different needs of children and ensures quality education through appropriate professional curricula teaching strategies support services and partnership with parents and the community for good personality development.

Therefore, Ikwulono (2017), noted that teachers should check well the psychosocial development of the child's classroom arrangement, the rules and regulations of the classroom, creating and reinforcing desirable behaviors, reducing and punishing undesirable behaviors, encouraging self-esteem and management. The professional teacher should endeavor to understand the homes the child comes from and the subtle socio-emotional pressures which shape their lives and being able to establish functional, social relationship with them.

Challenges of Inclusive Education in Teacher Preparation

Inclusive education provides an integral component of the overall educational system and is provided in regular school committed in an appropriate education for all. However, Ikwulono (2017) observed the following challenges in the teaching profession.

1. The School is not well equip with qualified manpower and material resources to service inclusive education programmes.
2. The personality attributes of the teacher are important to the learners, parents and the society because of the teachers sensitive function as a model.
3. The teacher is all the time under observation and evaluation because of the delicate and important roles he plays in classroom management in inclusive education setting.
4. Population explosion is a challenge teacher face in the setting as that gradually leads to discrimination among the various categories of the children.

Education system, calls for full acceptance and commendation of children with disabilities in the existing normal regular function of the school and classroom. Inclusive Education seems to “force” the regular school system to accept and accommodate children with special needs without the necessary and adequate preparation for these children. This could seriously affect and distort the smooth flow of Interest, purposes and teaching strategies, curriculum content of the school, teachers, students, parents and the community respectively.

Inclusion calls for demands from the inclusive school to equip themselves with qualified teachers and material resources. Programmes and activities, curricular content and needed support service to receive all categories of children with exceptionalities, to provide appropriate education and training for quality assurance. It solicits for the right type of values and attitudes for the survival of the child in the school and the community. Thus, the professional issues.

The acquisition of appropriate skills and value and the development of mental, physical, social and emotional competencies as instruments for the child with special needs to live and contribute to the development of self and Society. Inclusive education is costly and something has to be done, like provision of qualified teachers, conducive accommodation, instructional materials and equipment, regular identification and assessment of the children for proper placement and working with families of these children.

Functions of Special Need Education Teachers

Ikwulono (2012) observed the following functions of special needs education teachers in inclusive education setting:

1. Stimulation of the learners’ interest in learning and daily living skills development.
2. Motivation: The teacher appreciates the learner on any positive behavior exhibited by the learner by either giving a token, pat on either the head, back or a clap of the hands and positive verbal responses.
3. Guidance and Counseling Services: Here the teacher guides, Counsels and lead them for positive learning and development of appropriate and desirable behaviors for persons and social adequacies and learning.
4. Identification and referral services: The teacher identifies their individual problems and makes referral for early and quick intervention for remedy. Thus, to determine whether a child exhibits a developmental problem, what the problem is, its causes, and approaches to intervention and remediation and appropriate possible placement.

Conclusion

Excellent education policies are determined by professional teachers for their realization. If a child with special education needs is to survive and enjoy special education programme in Nigeria, teacher preparation should be geared towards professionalism like law, accountancy, medicine and architecture.

Suggestions

For a suitable teacher preparation for professionalism in Nigeria in inclusive setting, the following suggestions will be ideal:

1. The special education teacher should be professionally exposed to needs, interests, skills and potentials in special needs education to operate in any settings of human endeavors.
2. They should be motivated through regular training and re-training, good salary to sustain their interest to readily accept the nitty-gritty of the profession in inclusive setting.

3. There is high and urgent need for collaborative professional and non-professional support in both human and material resources to sustain the teachers.
4. The regular curriculum should be adapted and modified to reflect the learning needs of children with special needs for professionalism.
5. All special education teachers should go for compulsory retraining and development studies in inclusive education as special education is changing with the trends of events in the world.

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